

Cryogenic InGaAs HEMT-Based Switches For Quantum Signal Routing

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Abstract—We demonstrate cryogenic switching devices based on HEMT technology for scalable quantum computer (QC) control and readout signal routing. The switches are implemented in a quantum well network design without metal contacts between gates, and exhibit extremely steep cryogenic subthreshold swing of ~ 5 mV/decade, fast switching, along with on/off ratio of 10^7 and isolation leakage of 10 pA/ μm . The use of a Pt gate metal layer that diffuses into the gate barrier is shown to significantly enhance subthreshold properties. The results indicate that HEMT-based switching circuits could offer advantages over Si CMOS at cryogenic temperatures for future high-density ultra-low power QC signal routing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The impact of a mature quantum computing technology on society will be transformative [1], but to realize such a quantum technology, the whole quantum system must evolve, from the qubit chip to the readout and control electronics [2]. To control large numbers of physical qubits, cryogenic electronics may be necessary to some extent to reduce system cost, cabling and increase speed [3]. One of the main limitations of the design and integration of cryogenic electronics is the low cooling power available in the cryostat (in the order of W at 3 K and 100 μW at 10 mK). Advanced cryo-control circuits in CMOS dissipate 1-5 mW/qubit, meaning that scalability is still limited [4]. In addition, such circuits must likely be placed at different cryostat stages than the qubits due to thermal management, thus connecting the qubit and control chips remains a challenge. Multiplexing may offer a partial solution to these challenges, and is already used today, both in frequency domain, and through MEMS switches [5]. However, for dense and close integration with qubits, a switch technology tailored for qubit control signals, with extremely low power, low charge injection, fast switching, and without stray magnetic fields is desirable [2]. III-V HEMTs are an attractive option here and are already used in qubit readout LNAs due to their low power, low noise and high mobilities at cryogenic temperatures.

In this work, we demonstrate QC signal switches based on III-V HEMTs and characterize their switching properties at cryogenic temperatures. The switches show attractive cryogenic performance with fast switching in time domain and extremely steep turn-on/off characteristics. Compared to our previous work [6], the devices presented here have been significantly scaled down and have a Pt barrier diffusion gate layer, resulting in much improved cryogenic performance.

II. DEVICE DESIGN AND FABRICATION

The 1-to-2 switches in this work are envisioned as the building blocks for larger switches in a branching quantum well network (**Fig.1**). The branching shape ensures each path has

nominally the same impedance and can reduce the number of controllable gates, M , from M to $\ln(M)$ by coupling together, at each level of the network, all the orange (left) gates, and all the green (right) gates, indicated in Fig. 1 [7]. Thus, each level ends up with 2 gate lines to be controlled.

The devices are fabricated on a quantum well heterostructure formed by InGaAs, InAlAs and InP epitaxial layers, as shown in **Fig. 2**. The quantum well is 15 nm thick and the barrier 8 nm. Typical electron Hall mobility at 4 K is 40,000 cm^2/Vs . The outline of the quantum well structure is defined by electron beam lithography, followed by a wet etching process. The input and output contacts are then realized by evaporation of a Ni/Ge/Au metal stack and then annealed. Next, the gate recess is obtained by wet etching of the n^{++} InGaAs cap layer. A Pt/Ti/Pt/Au gate is then deposited inside the recess via evaporation; a TEM cross-section of the gate metal stack is shown in **Fig. 3**. Then, an Al_2O_3 passivation layer is deposited via atomic layer deposition (ALD) on the active region of the device and the metal probing pads are deposited. During the ALD, the Pt diffuses into the barrier layer, reducing the effective barrier thickness (**Fig. 3**) [8]. **Fig. 4** and **5** show SEM images of two completed devices studied in this work with slightly different geometries, the first with a T-shape and the second with a forked design.

III. RESULTS

Output characteristics of one branch of a scaled T-shaped switch (Fig. 3) with $L_G = 100$ nm is shown in **Fig. 6** at 4 and 300 K. Currents are normalized to the width of the branch under the gate, 635 nm (this is smaller than the main branch due to lateral etch from the recess etch step). Comparison with a larger switch design is shown in **Fig. 7**. The corresponding transfer characteristics for these devices are shown in **Fig. 8** and **9**. The scaled switch shows significantly higher transconductance due to reduced resistances in the cap layer. A comparison between the T-shaped and forked switch designs are shown in **Fig. 10**. The T-shaped design is slightly more compact and shows higher drain current. The output conductance, g_d , for the T-shaped device is shown in **Fig. 11**. Above $V_{GS} = 0.25$ V, negative g_d is observed. This is a typical sign of self-heating in the channel, caused by a reduction of the I_{DS} due to self-heating as the output power is increased. Self-heating is known to increase in FETs at cryogenic temperatures [9], and could introduce thermal noise to the qubit if the switch is operating very close to the qubit. Operation below 100 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$ does not show clear self-heating through reduced g_d .

In the following, we focus on the $L_G = 100$ nm T-shaped switch. Subthreshold characteristics from 300 to 4 K are shown

in **Fig. 12** at $V_{DS} = 0.4$ V. The minimum I_{OFF} is set by the gate leakage (**Fig. 13**) and is reduced by approximately 10x at 4 K due to reduced thermal leakage at the gate Schottky barrier. The device exhibits extremely steep turn-on/off characteristics. **Fig. 14** shows the subthreshold swing, SS, at $V_{DS} = 0.4$ V for devices with Pt bottom gate metal, and devices without Pt that we showed in [6]. The Pt-devices exhibit down to SS ~ 5 mV/decade at 4 K, and follow the thermal limit quite well down to ~ 20 K. This is among the lowest reported SS for FETs at this temperature [10]. Typically, a deviation from the thermal trend is observed around 50 K, with SS saturating around 10-20 mV/decade, which can be attributed to the presence of band tails or the inflection phenomenon [10][11]. The improvement from the diffused Pt is, in part, due to the reduced effective barrier thickness, and may also be due to an improved interface to the gate metal. Subthreshold properties, SS versus I_{DS} , are further shown in **Fig. 15**. For switches interfacing qubits, charge injection is an important effect to minimize, as it can disturb the qubit state. Steeper SS can be beneficial to reducing charge injection by allowing to operate with a lower overdrive voltage. This applies primarily to the signal feedthrough, i.e. the charge released by extrinsic capacitances. This charge is directly proportional to the voltage swing applied at the gate. Hence, a lower overdrive voltage results in a smaller charge injected by extrinsic capacitances.

The on-resistance, R_{ON} , is shown in **Fig. 16** versus T . R_{ON} can be described as $R_{ON} = R_{Cap} + 2R_C + 2R_B + R_{QW}$, where R_{Cap} is the resistance due to the sheet resistance of the n^+ cap layer, R_B is the resistance due to the tunneling barrier into the channel, and R_{QW} is the quantum well channel resistance. These resistances measured from recessed TLM versus T are shown in the inset. We observe that R_B is constant with T , R_{Cap} and R_{QW} are reduced at low T due to enhanced mobility, and R_C is increased at low T likely due to lower thermal injection at the contact Schottky barriers. Down to 50 K, the T-dependence of R_{ON} is dominated by R_{Cap} and R_{QW} , while below that, it is dominated by R_C . The increase of R_{ON} at 4 K by $\sim 20 \Omega\mu\text{m}$ matches the trend seen in R_C . This highlights the importance of R_C optimization for cryogenic operation of HEMTs.

The threshold voltage, V_T , is shown in **Fig. 17**, calculated by the constant current, second derivative and linear extrapolation methods. A small V_T -shift of around 100 mV towards enhancement mode is observed at 4 K.

To determine the switching speed, we estimate the transit time $\tau = 1/(2\pi f_i)$ through S-parameter measurements up to 67 GHz, **Fig. 18**. Since the W_G of the switches is too small to provide enough current for the VNA measurements, we measure here HEMTs on the same heterostructure with T-gates ($L_G = 100$ nm, $W_G = 2 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$) and GSG pad configuration. Room-temperature f_i/f_{max} were 321/369 GHz ($V_D = 0.8$ V, $I_D = 30$ mA). While significantly lower f_{max} and somewhat lower f_i is expected for the switches due to the different gate structure, a transit time and switching speed of around 1 ps is still expected. This is significantly faster than the current speed of quantum gate operations, which are $>1 \mu\text{s}$, and single control pulses, which are in the range of 10-50 ns [5].

Next, the cryogenic switching properties of a full 1-to-2 switch are analyzed using a 5-probe measurement setup. **Fig.**

19 shows the simultaneous transfer characteristics of the two branches, I_{D1} and I_{D2} with grounded output at equal V_D and V_G to study the symmetry. The two branches demonstrate similar current levels, V_T and off-state. The small difference may be due to a slight normalization error due to the difficulty of exactly estimating the gate width under the gate electrode.

Fig. 20 shows instead the input bias being swept from 0 to 0.6 V, with one branch turned on and the other turned off. This measures the isolation between branches. A fairly constant on/off-ratio of $\sim 10^7$ with a leakage into the off-path of approximately 10 pA/ μm is observed. This level of isolation is well sufficient to isolate two qubits from each other in a typical control operation. **Fig. 21**, finally, shows the isolation behavior when switching one branch on, while the other is off.

Test structures to investigate the benefit of the branching switch architecture (**Fig. 1**) were fabricated. Two structures – one with metal contacts, one without metal contacts, but both with the same length of the cap layer – are compared with the number of gates varying from 1 to 8. This represents the current path flowing through up to 8 levels of the switch in **Fig. 1**. **Fig. 22** shows images of these devices and their R_{ON} . Devices with metal contacts can be described as $R_{ON, \text{Met}} = M(R_{Cap} + 2R_B + R_{QW} + 2R_C)$, while the network design only has a fixed $2R_C$ contribution from the contacts, and the R_B becomes a resistor network between the quantum well and cap layers. As shown in **Fig. 22**, this results in a $\sim 30\%$ reduction of R_{ON} in the network design even for two-gate switches.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated cryogenic switches based on III-V quantum wells for multiplexed QC control and readout signals. The switches exhibit excellent cryogenic performance, and extremely low subthreshold swing of 5 mV/decade at 4 K, enhanced by Pt diffusion into the gate barrier, and is promising for reduced charge-injection, important for qubit control. In addition, we show that the metal contact-less switch design results in a 30% reduction of R_{ON} by lower R_C and barrier tunneling resistance. The results show that HEMT-based switches could offer a significant advantage over Si CMOS for ultra-low power QC signal routing, and can also enable monolithic integration with HEMT LNAs at qubit readout.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported as a part of NCCR SPIN, a National Centre of Competence in Research, funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (grant number 51NF40-180604), by the European Union H2020 program SEQUENCE (Grant – 871764), by the SNF Ambizione and the BRNC.

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Fig. 1. Schematic of envisioned cryogenic switching circuit comprised of a branching quantum well network heterostructure. In this work, we study the indicated 1-to-2 switch cell.

Fig. 2. Schematic figure of the cross-section of the T-shaped multiplexer cell indicated in Fig.1 from one contact metal to the other, spanning two gates. The layer thicknesses are not shown to scale.

Fig. 3. DF-TEM images of the gate stack and quantum well heterostructure. The right-hand side image shows a section of the stack. The Pt bottom metal has diffused into the InP top barrier, which effectively reduces the total barrier thickness.

Fig. 4. SEM image of a 1-to-2 T-shaped switch indicated in Fig. 1. The input-to-output distance is here $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$. The gate length is $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 5. SEM image of a forked switch design. This design corresponds to a circuit similar to Fig. 1 but with the gates perpendicular to the main current flow.

Fig. 6. Output characteristics of a small T-shaped switch with input-output distance $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 4), at room temperature and at 4K.

Fig. 7. Output characteristics of a larger switch with input-to-output distance of $10 \mu\text{m}$, at room temperature and at 4K.

Fig. 8. Transconductance as a function of the gate voltage of the small T-shaped switch (same as Fig. 6), at various temperatures.

Fig. 9. Transconductance as a function of the gate voltage of the larger switch (same as Fig. 7), at various temperatures.

Fig. 10. Comparison of transfer properties for the forked and T-shaped switch designs at 4 K and $V_{DS} = 0.4 \text{ V}$, similar to Fig. 4 and 5, with $L_G = 100 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 11. Output conductance of the T-shaped multiplexer (Fig. 6) at $V_{GS} = 0.3 \text{ V}$. Negative output conductance is observed at low temperatures, indicative of self-heating.

Fig. 12. Transfer characteristics of one gate from the T-shaped switch, measured at different temperatures and $V_{DS} = 0.4$ V.

Fig. 13. Gate leakage versus the gate voltage, shown at different temperatures. A reduction of more than an order of magnitude is observed at 4 K.

Fig. 14. Subthreshold swing of the T-shaped switch at different temperatures. Devices with and without Pt in the gate are compared.

Fig. 15. Subthreshold swing of the T-shaped switch at $V_{DS} = 0.4$ V, extracted as a function of the drain current at different temperatures.

Fig. 16. On-state resistance as function of the temperature. Inset shows the composing resistances determined from TLM measurements.

Fig. 17. Threshold voltage as a function of the temperature using different methods. A threshold voltage increase of around 100 mV is observed.

Fig. 18. Gain measured on a $L_G = 100$ nm T-gate device (inset) on the same heterostructure as the switches. Note that the switches will have lower mainly f_{max} due to not having a T-gate.

Fig. 19. Simultaneous transfer characteristics of the left and right branches of a 2-to-1 switch, measured at $T = 4$ K measured using a 5-probe setup, as shown in the inset schematic.

Fig. 20. Currents in the two branches of a switch versus input/drain bias (V_d). The first transistor is in the on-state and second is off, as controlled by V_{g1} and V_{g2} . This shows the isolation between branches.

Fig. 21. Currents through two branches of a switch at a constant V_d /input bias, where V_{g1} is gradually increased bringing the transistor the other branch constantly in the off state.

Fig. 22. Impact of the branching quantum well (QW) design compared to a design with metal contacts is investigated. (a) Simplified schematics of resistor circuits for the two designs. The branching QW design replaces the R_C and R_B between gates with a resistor network between cap and QW. (b) SEM images of the fabricated test structures. Devices with 1 to 8 gates were fabricated. (c) On-resistance versus number of gates for the test structures. The QW structure shows $\sim 30\%$ lower R_{ON} due to reduction of the R_C and R_B .